

Correlation Analysis of Reactivity in the Oxidation of Substituted Aromatic Anils by Pyridinium Fluorochromate

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Very effective and interesting oxidising agent of chromium(VI), pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) has been reported recently¹. It is being increasingly used as an oxidant for several classes of organic compounds. Though the versatility of PFC as an oxidant is known², the study on the oxidation of nitrogen-containing compounds with PFC is rare. Here, we report the kinetics of oxidation of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted aromatic anils by PFC. Attempts have been made to correlate structure and reactivity in the reaction.

Results and Discussion

The results of kinetic investigations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SALIENT FEATURES OF KINETIC INVESTIGATION

Analysis	Observation	Inference
log [PFC] vs time	Linear ($r = 0.998$)	First order w.r.t. PFC
log k_1 vs log [anil]	Linear with unit slope	First order w.r.t. anil
log k_1 vs log $[H^+]$	Linear with slope ≈ 2	Second order w.r.t. H^+ ; two protons may involve in the slow step
Effect of $[NaClO_4]$	Rate of reaction reduced	Involvement of ionic species in reaction
Effect of $[Mn^{II}]$	Appreciable decrease in rate	Two-electron change in the slow step ^a
Effect of acrylonitrile	No effect	No free radical intermediate
Grunwald-Winstein equation	Linear ($r = 0.998$)	S_N2 type transition state
log $k_2 = \log k_0 + mY$	$m = -0.79$	
log k_2 vs Y		
Isokinetic relationship	Linear	All the anils are oxidised by the same mechanism ^b
log k_2 (30°) vs log k_2 (40°)	($r = 0.998$)	
Hammett equation	Linear	Electron-releasing groups increase the rate
log k_1 vs σ	($r = 0.998$) ($\rho = -2.01$)	
Product analysis	M.p., uv and derivative	Benzaldehyde, azobenzene
Stoichiometry	1 : 1	

^aRef. 5. ^bRefs. 3, 4.

The rates of oxidation of the substituted anils were measured at three different temperatures. The activation parameters are presented in Table 2. Based on the kinetic results the following tentative mechanism is proposed.

The above mechanism leads to the following rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[PFC]}{dt} = K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{anil}] [PFC] [H^+]^2$$

The rate law in its final form accounts for the observed kinetics as enumerated earlier. A linear isokinetic relationship was observed between log k_2 at 30° and log k_2 at 40°

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substituent	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H	52.4	47.7	101.4
<i>p</i> -Cl	46.6	45.1	108.2
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	59.1	63.7	73.7
<i>p</i> -OMe	57.4	61.1	78.8
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	43.3	35.6	125.6
<i>m</i> -Me	53.1	52.5	96.7
<i>m</i> -Cl	47.2	44.6	109.6

for the oxidation of seven aromatic anils. This suggests that all the anils are oxidised by the same mechanism. Further, a linear kinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationship³⁻⁶.

Experimental

Aromatic anils containing substituents in the benzalde-

NOTE

hyde moiety were prepared and purified by standard methods⁷. PFC was prepared by the literature method¹. Acetic acid was refluxed over chromic oxide for 5 h and then fractionated. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of the substrate over PFC. The reactions were followed by standard iodometric procedures

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